

11th Conference on Learning Factories, CLF2021

Plug-and-Play and Reconfigurable Transport Network Architecture to Put into Practice Connectivity and Interoperability in Learning Factories

Rafael A. Rojas^a, Benedikt G. Mark^a, Matteo De Marchi^{a,*}, Erwin Rauch^a,
Dominik T. Matt^{a,b}

^aIndustrial Engineering and Automation (IEA), Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Piazza Università 1, 39100 Bolzano, Italy

^bInnovation Engineering Center (IEC), Fraunhofer Italia Research s.c.a.r.l., Via A. Volta 13a, 39100 Bolzano, Italy

Abstract

Achieving interoperability between disparate digital systems is a major challenge for Industry 4.0 and a necessary step to build the digital representation of a factory. Despite all available technologies, there is still a gap between information technologies and manufacturing systems in terms of interoperability. In this paper, we address such a gap from the perspectives of learning factories and propose a plug and play and reconfigurable transport network layer, which makes it possible to exchange information at all levels of the factory floor. For the validation of the developed concept, an experimental setup of an assembly line is set up in the Smart Mini Factory learning factory laboratory and a didactic teaching concept is proposed. The paper aims to encourage other learning factories to install such plug and play reconfigurable transport network architectures and to use it for demonstration and teaching purposes of connectivity and interoperability in cyber-physical production systems.

© 2021 The Authors. This is an open access article.

Peer Review statement: Peer-review under responsibility of the scientific committee of the 11th Conference on Learning Factories 2021.

Keywords: Transport Network Architecture; Interoperability; Connectivity; Industry 4.0; Cyber-Physical Systems

1. Introduction

Nowadays, manufacturing companies find themselves in an increasingly volatile environment [1]. Megatrends such as digitalization, globalization, and sustainability and their associated effects are already noticeable [2]. In these surroundings, companies need to show their ability for innovation, since process and product innovations build a central lever for ensuring long-term competitiveness [3]. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SME), in particular, face increased difficulty to exploit and integrate such innovations effectively [4, 5]. Studies revealed the biggest restraints as missing organizational structures, financial risks, a lack in technological knowledge, and a deficit in possibilities for acquiring this knowledge [4, 6]. To approach the process of continuously learning, Learning- and Innovation-Factories (LIF) as well as Innovation Laboratories (InnoLabs) have been set up which are associated with “learning factories”. This term consists of the words “learning” and “factory” and describes innovative and practice-oriented teaching methods in a realistic industrial environment with real industrial products [7]. Through learning factories, a significant help can be given regarding education of employees, training, update of intellectual capital in industry, and a constant modernization [8] representing an optimal experience and qualification environment for SMEs. In this paper, we present the design, prototyping and implementation of a manufacturing service bus (MSB), i.e., a middleware infrastructure which creates a uniform channel for information flow among disparate platforms capable of supporting an event-driven system. This MSB is deployed on the top a transport network layer created to integrate disparate digital and cyber-physical systems (CPS) present

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +39 0471017220
E-mail address: matteo.demarchi@natec.unibz.it

on many manufacturing environments, an electric screwdriver and a robot with an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) software. In Section 2 we provide the theoretical background. In Section 3, we briefly describe the methodology for the design of the plug-and-play MSB. In Section 4 we present the components of our manufacturing test-case and their connectivity requirements. In Section 5 we present the results, the conclusion and the future work. This section also specifically addresses the relevance of these topics for learning factories and the need to integrate applicability into the learning concept of our educational institution as well.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. Cyber-Physical Production Systems in Learning Factories

During the fourth industrial revolution, the creation of data dramatically increased, due to the high amount of data-creation enabled entities available in industry, such as sensors, devices, logistics vehicles and also humans [9]. Thanks to the enhanced information mining from manufacturing facilities and assembly lines, it is possible to create virtual emulations of the real world in form of CPS. Based on the data flow characteristics that put into communication the real world with the virtual environment and vice versa, it is possible to distinguish among three levels of integration. In a *digital model* configuration, data from the real world are fed manually to the digital system and its output are manually transferred back to the real world. A *digital shadow* is established if there is an automated data flow from the shop floor towards the digital system, while also in this case there is no backwards connection. Instead, when considering the *digital twin* paradigm, the data flow assumes the characteristics of a loop. In fact, the abstraction of data from the real world is ran automatically for feeding artificial intelligence (AI) based algorithms, which, in turn, send commands back to the shop floor, influencing the behavior of the physical system [10]. Even though the ability of creating massive amount of data could be perceived as the ultimate goal, this generates instead issues and challenges, such as data volume, accessibility, processing and complexity [11]. The development and implementation of cyber-physical production systems (CPPS) has grown during the last decade, but the accessibility to the enabling technologies and methods, as well as the fear of change and the lack of expertise, are often insurmountable barriers [12].

With the objective of demonstrating the potential of CPPS implementation and for transferring knowledge from the academic environment to the industrial one, learning factories must come into play. In fact, the non-formal learning approach [13] offered by hands-on demonstrations and trainings in learning factories assure a tailored experience to engineering students, which are more inclined to be “visual learners” [14]. The learning factory teaching style could be particularly effective when treating topics that are abstract and implementable at the same time, meaning that students can follow a path that brings them from the pure theory to a practical implementation. In the next section, the concept of interoperability is introduced, as one of the enabling factors of the CPPS paradigm [15].

2.2. Interoperability and SOA

Contrary to what common sense could say, heterogeneity of components in modern industrial systems may be a favorable [16] as the incorporation of components from multiple distributors with different technologies may improve flexibility and efficiency. Moreover, in the context of cloud manufacturing where the geographic distribution of manufacturing span different standards and legal constraints many applications may require unique and disparate implementations. In fact, CPS are intrinsically heterogeneous systems due to the natural difference between physical behavior, design concepts and modelling methods that characterize each component of a CPS. Historically, the evolution of integration between digital systems begins with point-to-point integration solutions and has evolved in the implementation of the so-called service oriented architectures (SOA) [17] to assure flexibility and loosely coupled systems. In parallel, communication solutions in industrial automation systems also begin using point-to-point solutions that were expensive and bulky [18]. In the two fields, enterprise management and industrial automation, a single cable of communication where electrical signals exchange data, also called a bus, was a good metaphor for the desired solution capable to substitute each point-to-point solution by a bus-like installation capable of connecting all devices via a shared medium. In higher level enterprise application integration appears the term enterprise service bus (ESB) to describe the software infrastructure capable of emulating such a bus and in the field of industrial automation the term Fieldbus was coined.

Unlike ESB, Fieldbuses were originally developed for embedded systems (ES) with reduced resources designed to exchange little amount of data with stringent timing requirements. With the introduction of CPS on the factory shop floor, the quality of the exchanged information becomes more similar to higher level systems. Instead of exchanging positions of servos, a CPS may receive complex information regarding the geometry or other

features of a product to be assembled. Examples of CPS integration may be found also in [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 17].

3. Methodology

We follow the European Telecommunication Standards Institute [25] to identify three kinds of interoperability: (i) technical, (ii) syntactic and (iii) sematic. With technical interoperability we refer to the capacity of exchanging raw and autonomous sequence of bites. Syntactic interoperability is associated with data formats, i.e., the symbols represented by such sequences of bits. Finally, semantic interoperability is the capacity of exchanging meaning between systems. Semantic interoperability depends on syntactic interoperability that depends on technical interoperability. We will build technical interoperability and a first level of the plug-and-play capacity using the OSI layers 1-4 and syntactic interoperability using OSI layers 4-7. At the OSI layer 3 we will use the Ethernet IP protocol and at the OSI layer 4 we implement TCP and UDP. The UDP protocol is used to implement the plug-and-play feature by solving two different problems, one related to identification of host in a IP network and another related to discover which services a host provides. When IPs are automatically assigned using DHCP technology, is it not possible to known a priori, which IP is assigned to which machine. This constraint is generally avoided by using static IP assignment. However, this solution requires an IP-assignment process, which is slow and requires the intervention of the IT-management team, adding complexity to the system deployment. In order to ensure the “plug-and-play” ability we implement the BounJour technology [26]. This technology allows to automatically discover devices on an IP network with automatic IP assignment by using the multicasting DNS (mDNS) protocol. This protocol allows to automatically interrogate all compatible host in a network with a minimum consumption of bandwidth. Moreover, it allows having host resolution via semantically meaningful names rather than IP’s and interrogate each host about the services it provides. To achieve syntactic interoperability, we use the TCP protocol at the OSI 4 layer and at the OSI layers 5-7 we use the XMLRPC protocol. In particular, we implement on the robot and on the screwdriver the standard Python3 XMLRPC library. Such library has two main advantages. On the one hand, this library is available in almost any Linux-based system because it is part of the minimal Python3 installation. This gives flexibility to our approach. On the other hand, it provides a service discovery capability, i.e., the capability of asking a given service the specificities of each remote procedure calls that it exposes.

However, not all systems that we address have the Ethernet compatibility. In order to ensure uniform access to the OSI layer 7 to these systems, we will build a so-called I4.0 shell or I.40 gateway [20]. An I.40 gateway is an attachment to an embedded system that acts as a bridge between low-level communication interfaces such as I4C, SMP and On/Off signals, and high level interfaces such as those at the OSI layer 7.

4. Design and Implementation

4.1. Component Description

The MSB implementation presented in this paper puts into communication two main actors, namely a collaborative robot and an industrial screwdriver. A microcontroller is needed for enabling screwdriver’s connectivity. The collaborative robot chosen for this project is the model Universal Robots UR3: it is designed for both, assembly and workbench tasks, where the payload does not exceed 3 kg. It is a 6-axis manipulator constituted by and anthropomorphic base and a three-axis wrist with a workspace capable of reaching 500mm. The robot’s controller is composed by two cards, one is a dedicated controller for the robot, safety, digital and analog IOS, the other is a Mini-ITX with little-endian i686 architecture 4-core Intel CPU (output of lscpu). The hardware is managed by a Linux operating system which runs, as a daemon, the low-level robot controller called URControl. It also has two network interface cards (NIC) with IEEE 802.3u 100BASE-TX Ethernet capability. One is exclusively used to communicate with the controller card and the other is available to the user. A visual interface is available through a touch screen pendant, providing a graphic user interface (GUI) called PolyScope. The actual commands to the robot’s joints are handled with the URControl daemon. The most interesting feature of the UR3 for hybrid assembly is that its design is oriented for safe physical human-robot interaction (pHRI). It was designed according to the standards ISO 10218 and ISO/TS 15066.

One of the main advantages of having Linux Debian as OS, is that it has a natural compatibility with the technologies we use. In particular, such a system allows installing BonJour technology via the zeroconf package and the XMLRPC technology via the standard python packages. The electric screwdriver employed in this project is a standard Fiam eTensil E8C3A-1200 and is driven by a Fiam TPU2 controller. The screwdriver has a maximum tightening torque of 3 Nm and features torque-control driven automatic shut off. On the back of the screwdriver’s controller there is a DB15 standard connector which provides digital input/output (I/O) capabilities. Through the

I/O it is possible to start and stop tightening, start and stop untightening and to modify the rotational speed (high or low). The screwdriver can provide feedback about its state (ready or not, rotating or not), about the activation of the clutch and about errors detected by the controller. In order to provide connectivity to the screwdriver system, it is necessary interface screwdriver's I/O with a microcontroller. For satisfying the requirements of this project, a Raspberry Pi 4, with 4 GB RAM, has been adopted. This microcontroller provides satisfactory computational power (in relation to the needs of the project), it comes with a built-in Wi-Fi module, it offers 40 General Purpose Input Output (GPIO) pins, and it is suitable for the execution of Python scripts. Thanks to these characteristics, the Raspberry Pi 4 is particularly appropriate for the implementation of this project. From a general perspective, the Raspberry Pi microcontroller family is well renowned for its flexibility and ease-of-use, especially in prototyping and tinkering projects. Thanks to its contained price and the vast documentation, it is often a better choice with respect to more professional products, especially in learning environments, whereas evidences of its exploitation in learning factories are also found in literature [27, 28, 29]. The ERP that we consider is Microsoft Dynamics. Such a software has the possibility of creating custom XMLRPC calls for each desired situation. Thus, this system comes already integrated into our MSB.

4.2. 14.0 Gateway Developing

An electrical circuit interfacing the screwdriver and the microcontroller is required due to the different voltage at which each system operates (Fig. 1). Namely, the screwdriver is operated at 24 V, while the microcontroller operates at 3,3 V. It is evident that the two actors cannot be directly connected one to another, otherwise, the one running at higher voltage will out burn the other. To connect the two systems in an electrically safe manner, isolating components, such as optocouplers, must be employed.

Optocouplers are electronic components that transfer electrical signals between two isolated circuits by using light. The optocouplers (or opto-isolators) used for implementing the prototype are of 4N35 type and are composed of a Led Emitting Diode (LED) and a Negative-Positive-Negative (NPN) phototransistor. The actor sending the signal is connected to the anode (signal source) (prior an adequate resistor) and to the cathode (ground), so that when a "high" signal is provided, the LED turns on. The collector must be connected to a voltage source, which must provide the same voltage tolerated by the system that receives the signal. The emitter is finally connected to the input designated pin of the receiving system. The input side of the optocouplers (anode and cathode) is easily identified thanks to the presence of a dot printed or engraved on its the surface: the side marked with the dot is where the outputting system must be connected. The systems that become connected through an optocoupler are physically isolated one from the other. When the outputting system does not produce any signal (no current flowing through the LED that does not emit light), the phototransistor acts as an open circuit and there will be no current flowing from the collector to the emitter (the input pin will be perceived as "low" by the receiving system).

Fig. 1. Interface circuit design.

Instead, when the outputting system applies a voltage difference among the anode and the cathode, the LED will turn on, affecting the behavior of the phototransistor, which will now act as a short circuit. It must be underlined, that when the phototransistor acts as a short circuit, the amount of current flowing in the system could be unacceptably high. This could cause overheating and breakage of the receiving system. This issue must be taken into consideration beforehand, by correctly choosing a resistor to be applied between the emitter and the input pin of the receiving system. Pull-up or pull-down resistors could be implemented to modify the behavior of the designated input pin on the receiving system, which will act as normally closed if the circuit foresees a pull-up resistor, or as normally open if the circuit includes a pull-down resistor. Thanks to the above-described approach, it is possible to design an electronical circuit, in charge of putting into communication the Raspberry Pi with the screwdriver, as shown in Fig. 1. Reminding that the final objective of this project is to implement a plug-and-play MSB it is necessary to design a software component capable of exchanging information along the different layers of the OSI, comprising the eight previously mentioned in paragraph 3. For this prototype, the communication among the collaborative robot and the screwdriver happens at local level through a proximity network, thanks to XML-RPC calls. A Python package running on the Raspberry Pi oversees the encapsulation- and decapsulation processes. Due to the features of the XML-RPC Python library, it is possible to expose the methods of the class in charge of sending and receiving commands to and from the screwdriver's controller. By doing so, any device connected to the proximity network can easily interact with the screwdriver, exploiting the dedicated methods. This result in the possibility of remotely managing the functioning of the screwdriver, together with the possibility of remotely receiving feedback from it. The scripts have been successfully tested using the Unit Testing framework.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The achievement of interoperability between disparate digital systems is a crucial challenge for Industry 4.0. Even though there is a large number of available technologies, a gap in the degree of integration between manufacturing systems and information technologies can be still noticed. In this paper, the authors addressed this gap and propose a plug and play, reconfigurable transport network layer to be employed in a learning factory environment. Therefore, the authors built up an experimental setup of an assembly line and tested the realized system, which is a first step in the creation of a plug and play MSB for learning factories as well as for real world applications. Overall, the results were satisfying, and a working data flow could be created which opens the opportunity to integrate also other systems. Subsequently, together with a support, the screwdriver can be mounted on the collaborative robot as an endeffector, making the device also automatically moveable. An advantage of the system is the possibility to control the system remotely. This is not only the case for direct control of the screwdriver, but also for feedback given from the screwdriver to the user. This use case, therefore, represents a suitable project for learning factories and is a tangible example. By applying this methodology and technique, the project can be enlarged in terms of integration of other devices into the overall learning factory's system. In addition to the concept for creating the system, the basic idea of the learning factory should not be neglected. As mentioned in the introduction, a learning factory describes a practice-oriented teaching method in a realistic industrial environment with real industrial products. Therefore, the concepts and implementations shown here must also be integrated into the curriculum in the best possible way in order to familiarize the students with the complete concept. Specially designed courses within the LFs can introduce students to these concepts and processes and give them a feeling for overarching projects. For this purpose, it makes sense to have open structures within the learning factory, like those found in a team in practice, which convey a sense of community. Here, the team concept should be conveyed above all during implementation. Thus, this training could differ from the classical training in that the feeling of jointly working out aspects already starts there. The LF as such is thus not to be seen as a pure place of learning, but offers space for exchange, which in itself reflects practical relevance. However, the basic methods and aspects to be taught must not be neglected. Once a sense of practice and teamwork has been created, it is important to give students the ability to view processes and work steps with a higher-level perspective. This can be taught through various practice courses. In addition, interdisciplinarity of the different areas must be shown in order to give the students a general knowledge of software and hardware. In the future, a stronger fusion of informatics with engineering approaches will be required. Through protected environments, such as those of the LFs, these skills can be integrated into the didactic concept and curriculum. However, there are limitations that must be addressed. Due to the fact that the project was conducted with a microcontroller that operates at lower voltage with respect to the one of the screwdriver, an additional power supply was required. Another limitation that is caused by the screwdriver characteristics is the restricted possibilities of I/O on the screwdriver, which causes a limited interaction of the system. Making the screwdriver behave as a collaborative robot's endeffector represent the next milestone of this project. The precision of the self-built supporting device will have to be machined with high precision to grant reliable in-the-field applications.

In future, the creation of a web interface is planned, with the objective to interact with the screwdriver from any device in both directions and to integrate also other middleware. In addition, the expansion of the I/O capability of the screwdriver opens new possibilities to interact with the device.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 R&I programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 734713.

References

- [1] E. Zahn, "Strategische Unternehmensführung zur Ko-Evolution von Unternehmen und Umwelt," in *Technologie, Strategie und Organisation*, W. Burr and M. Stephan, Eds. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien, 2017, pp. 193–215.
- [2] M. Schmitz, "Erstellung der Suchstrategie," *Technologien frühzeitig erkennen, Nutzenpotenziale systematisch bewerten*, pp. 14–22, 2015.
- [3] P. Pohl and H. Kempermann, *Innovative Milieus: Die Innovationsfähigkeit deutscher Unternehmen*. BertelsmannStiftung, IW Consult, 2020.
- [4] K. Lichtblau, T. Schleiermacher, H. Goecke, and P. Schützdeller, "Digitalisierung der KMU in Deutschland," *Köln: IW Consult*, p. 28, 2018.
- [5] A. J. Freimark, J. Habel, S. Huelsboemer, B. Schmitz, and M. Teichmann, "Hidden Champions—Champions of the Digital Transformation?," *IDG Research Services*, 2018.
- [6] C. Rammer, S. Gottschalk, B. Peters, J. Bersch, and D. Erdsiek, "Die Rolle von KMU für Forschung und Innovation in Deutschland: Studie im Auftrag der Expertenkommission Forschung und Innovation," *Studien zum deutschen Innovationssystem*, 2016.
- [7] U. Wagner, T. AlGeddawy, H. ElMaraghy, and E. Mýller, "The state-of-the-art and prospects of learning factories," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 3, pp. 109–114, 2012.
- [8] E. Abele, J. Metternich, and M. Tisch, *Learning Factories - Concepts, Guidelines, Best-Practice Examples*. .
- [9] J. Wang, W. Zhang, Y. Shi, S. Duan, and J. Liu, "Industrial Big Data Analytics: Challenges, Methodologies, and Applications," Jul. 03, 2018.
- [10] W. Kritzinger, M. Karner, G. Traar, J. Henjes, and W. Sihn, "Digital Twin in manufacturing: A categorical literature review and classification," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 51, no. 11, pp. 1016–1022, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2018.08.474.
- [11] M. Marjani et al., "Big IoT Data Analytics: Architecture, Opportunities, and Open Research Challenges," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 5247–5261, 2017, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2689040.
- [12] A. A. Neto, F. Deschamps, E. R. da Silva, and E. P. de Lima, "Digital twins in manufacturing: an assessment of drivers, enablers and barriers to implementation," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 93, pp. 210–215, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.procir.2020.04.131.
- [13] M. Tisch, E. Abele, and J. Metternich, "Learning in Production, Learning for Production," in *Learning Factories : Concepts, Guidelines, Best-Practice Examples*, E. Abele, J. Metternich, and M. Tisch, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 59–79.
- [14] R. Felder, "Learning and Teaching Styles in Engineering Education," *Journal of Engineering Education -Washington-*, vol. 78, pp. 674–681, Jan. 1988.
- [15] K. E. Harper, C. Ganz, and S. Malakuti, "Digital Twin Architecture and Standards," Nov. 2019.
- [16] S.-W. Lin and B. Miller, "Industrial internet: towards interoperability and composability," Technical Report, Industrial Internet Consortium, June 2016. Available ..., 2016.
- [17] D. Chen, G. Doumeings, and F. Vernadat, "Architectures for enterprise integration and interoperability: Past, present and future," *Computers in industry*, vol. 59, no. 7, pp. 647–659, 2008.
- [18] M. Felser, "The fieldbus standards: History and structures," *Technology Leadership Day*, 2002.
- [19] M. Pérez-Lara, J. A. Saucedo-Martínez, J. A. Marmolejo-Saucedo, T. E. Salais-Fierro, and P. Vasant, "Vertical and horizontal integration systems in Industry 4.0," *Wireless Networks*, pp. 1–9, 2018.
- [20] L. Monostori et al., "Cyber-physical systems in manufacturing," *Cirp Annals*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 621–641, 2016.
- [21] A. Boyd et al., "Soa in manufacturing guidebook," *MESA International, IBM Corporation and Capgemini co-branded white paper*, 2008.
- [22] L. M. S. De Souza, P. Spiess, D. Guinard, M. Köhler, S. Karnouskos, and D. Savio, "Socrates: A web service based shop floor integration infrastructure," in *The internet of things*, Springer, 2008, pp. 50–67.
- [23] A. W. Colombo et al., "Industrial cloud-based cyber-physical systems," *The lmc-aesop Approach*, vol. 22, pp. 4–5, 2014.
- [24] J. Minguez, F. Ruthardt, P. Riffelmacher, T. Scheibler, and B. Mitschang, "Service-based integration in event-driven manufacturing environments," in *International Conference on Web Information Systems Engineering*, 2010, pp. 295–308.
- [25] "ETSI - European Telecommunication Standards Institute," *ETSI*. <https://www.etsi.org/> (accessed Mar. 03, 2021).
- [26] V. Miori, D. Russo, and L. Ferrucci, "Interoperability of home automation systems as a critical challenge for IoT," in *2019 4th International Conference on Computing, Communications and Security (ICCCS)*, 2019, pp. 1–7.
- [27] B. Brenner and V. Hummel, "A Seamless Convergence of the Digital and Physical Factory Aiming in Personalized Product Emergence Process (PPEP) for Smart Products within ESB Logistics Learning Factory at Reutlingen University," in *Procedia CIRP*, 2016, vol. 54, pp. 227–232, doi: 10.1016/j.procir.2016.06.108.
- [28] A. Aljinović, N. Gjeldum, M. Crnjac, and M. Mladineo, "Analysis of performances of RFID systems for assembly line purposes in learning Factory," in *Mech. Technol. Struct. Mater.*, 2019, vol. 2019-September, no. 70, pp. 1–7, [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85075173444&partnerID=40&md5=2ce7bd861e81eea590f7e3633d852bad>.
- [29] M. Wiech, J. Böllhoff, and J. Metternich, "Development of an Optical Object Detection Solution for Defect Prevention in a Learning Factory," *Procedia Manuf.*, vol. 9, pp. 190–197, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.promfg.2017.04.037.